

Weight of Diabetic Patients in Shahkund Block Bhagalpur

Paper Id : 20652 Submission Date : 2025-08-11 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-21 Publication Date : 2025-08-25

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.17264107

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/remarking.php#8>

Rahul Kumar Raj

Ph.D.
P.G. Department Of Home
Science (Food & Nutrition)
T.M.Bhagalpur University
Bhagalpur, Bihar, India

Abstract

Diabetes is commonly disorder of carbohydrates metabolism and is characterized by high blood sugar level and also presence of sugar in urine .Polyurea, thirst are major symptoms of diabetes. In diabetic condition body does not produce enough insulin, finally causing abnormally high blood sugar. Obesity increases the risk of diabetes. Diabetes is silent killer, if People want to control diabetes ,must follow balance diet, avoid sugar based food and regular exercise. otherwise diabetes increases the risk of kidney dysfunction, vision loss, heart failure etc.

Two types of diabetes such as Type 1: IDDM (Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus) and Type 2: NIDDM (Non-Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus).Aims and objective of my study is to know the weight of diabetic patients . study is carried out with total number of Respondents(500).Data collected by direct interview method ,Questionnaire method. My study is divided in to Introduction, Aims and Objective, Hypothesis, Methodology, Data Collection and Analysis, Conclusion, Recommendation and References.

Keywords

Polyurea, Thirst, Insulin, Disorder, Vision loss, Heart failure Diet, Exercise

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is commonly called Diabetes. Hyperglycemia (high blood sugar) and sugar in the urine are symptoms of diabetes, a metabolic condition caused by problems with carbohydrate metabolism (glycosuria).This disease is most serious and affects human being.

When the body breaks down sugar and carbohydrates into glucose, the bloodstream distributes it to every cell in the body. When insulin is unable to do its job properly, it can lead to the development of type 2 diabetes. Insulin, a hormone, is produced by Langerhans, an endocrine component of the pancreas. Insulin deficiency can be either absolute or relative. Absolute deficiency of insulin is a rare condition. Diabetes mellitus can be controlled with a proper diet. If a proper diet is not followed, it can aggravate the situation and lead to some major health complications including: Eye disorder leading to vision loss, Thickening of arteries, and Kidney malfunction. Successful diabetes control is based on a well-planned diet, exercise, and insulin management.

Objective of study

1. To know the weight of diabetic patients
2. To know the awareness regarding their weight reducing or controlled weight.

Review of Literature

A comprehensive review of literature is the essential part of Research work. Review of literature becomes vital because the opinions of several authors, scientists or researchers are helpful and enables the researcher to work or to determine the prevalence of the problem (among people of Shahkund Block and to know the weight of Diabetic Patients).

Winkleby et. al. (1992) shows that the individuals who attained higher education may be considered to have more information regarding prevention and higher ability to change their bad lifestyle for their good health.

Ramachandran et. al. (2001) and the National Survey of diabetes were conducted in six major cities in India (2000) reported that the prevalence of diabetes in urban adults was 12.1%.The prevalence of impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) was also high (14.0%).

Hu et. al (2001) pointed out that it was widely accepted that lifestyle variables play a role in the development of type II diabetes mellitus. Lifestyle variables such as physical inactivity sedentary, cigarette smoking, and consumption of alcohol increase the risk of contracting Diabetes. Overweight or obesity also causes the risk of diabetes.

National Institute of Health (NIH) by K.Yashi 2023 Chavvi Garg; Sharon F.Daley, according to them excess body weight and obesity are significant risk factors for type 2 diabetes.so self management is necessary to reduced obesity.

World J.Diabetes.2024 May 15 . Overweight and obesity represent a growing threat for modern society and people with T1DM and the use of adjuncts to insulin therapy that have the potential to alleviate cardiorenal risk and decrease body weight can reduce the burden of obesity in patients with T1DM 52% increase in the adds of kidn ey disease.

Main Text

Types of Diabetes: Two kinds of Diabetes have been observed: **Type –1 Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM) or Juvenile-Onset type**

This type of diabetes occurs characteristically with an abrupt onset in patients who are less than 25-year-old. About 10-20% of reported cases are Type – I Diabetes. Because Beta cells get killed in Type-1 Diabetes, there is insufficient insulin delivery to maintain blood glucose levels. The reasons for the destruction of Beta – cells may be due to the interaction of drugs, viral infection, genetic aberration, this type of diabetic person requires insulin therapy for the control of diabetes. **Type – II Non-Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM) or The Maturity Onset Type:** 80-90% of known cases are of Type –2 ,in this type of Diabetes insulin production may be normal, increased or decreased. Tragic events in the family weight are another contributory factor that enhances the diseases. This type of Diabetes problem develops in middle-aged persons usually with obese patients.

Blood Glucose Level Fasting Blood Sugar Test: A Fasting blood sugar level less than 100 mg/dL indicates normally. When the blood sugar level is between 100-125 mg/dL, it indicates that the person is prediabetic and that above 126 mg/dL indicates Diabetes.

Methodology

The study has been carried out with 500 Respondents. Information was collected by questionnaire method, and by observation and interview method as possible. Data have been collected randomly from each family and results have been tabulated and analyzed by using proper techniques to make the research work.

Analysis

Table. Weights of Respondents

Weight Group		40 Kg	41-50 Kg	51-60 Kg	61-70 Kg	71-80 Kg	81-90 Kg	91-100 Kg	>100 Kg	Total
Number of Respondents	Male	5 1.38%	43 11.94%	127 35.27%	130 36.11%	49 13.61%	6 1.66%	00 0%	00 0%	360 72%
	Female	2 1.42%	16 11.42%	49 35%	46 32.85%	20 14.28%	7 5%	00 0%	00 0%	140 28%

Table shows, the weight of the respondents, the weight is divided into 8 groups, i.e from 40 kg to more than 100 kg. In this table male respondents, i.e 360, only 5 respondents were under 40 kg, 43 (11.94%) respondents between 41-50 kg, 127 (35.27%) respondents between 51-60 kg and a maximum of 130 (36.11%) respondents were in the weight group of 61-70 kg. and between 70-90 kg, (49+6) respondents were in this categories, none were above in group of 90 kg and 100 kg of weight. Out of 140 female respondents, only 2 (1.42%) respondents were found under 40 kg of weight, 16 (11.42%) and 14.28% (20 respondents) were from 41-50 kg and 71-80 kg of weight respectively. Between 51-60 kg, 49 (35%) respondents and 46 (32.85%) respondents were in the weight group of 61-70 kg respectively. Only 7 (5%) female respondents were found between 81-90 kg of weight. None were in the group of 91 kg and above. So the Total number of Male respondents were 72 % and female respondents were 28% respectively out of 100%.

The above table shows that the maximum weight of respondents was between 50-70 kg and above. This shows that as weight increases the risk of diabetes also increases. Therefore it can be assumed that body weight has an important role in the increase or decrease of the diabetic condition of a person. If the body weight is controlled the risk of diabetes can be monitored and controlled. It shows that there is a relation between body weight and diabetic problems.

Conclusion

Finding result is not satisfactory, maximum weight of respondents were in between 70 kg and above. Weight increases the risk of diabetes, body weight has an important role in increase or decrease of the diabetic condition. I therefore recommend that body weight is controlled by respondents ,balance diet pattern and regular exercise should be followed by them, specially those who are facing diabetic condition.

References

1. *Diabetes in the UK 2011/2012: Key statistic on diabetes.*
2. Lydia A. Bazzano, Tricia yli, Kamudi J Joshipura, Frank; *Intake of fraits vegetables and fruits juice and risk of diabetes in woman. Diabetes case 31(7), 1311-1317, 2008: case diabetes Journals. org.*
3. Renu Vadiyanathan: *The week Health November 20, 2011*
4. Dr SK. Wangnoo (Senior consultant, A pollo centre for obesity diabetes and endocrinology in Delhi): *The week Health November 20, 2011.*
5. Edralin Lucas: *Ph.D Associate professor of Nutritional science at ok lahoma state university : college of Human Science, 9 sep, 2014 ; Journal : Nutrition and Metabolisms.*
6. World Health organization: *Global Health Expenditure Diabeses General Government Expenditure on health (GGHE) as the % 2012 [16.10.2014]: <http://apps.who.int/nha/database/select/Indicator>.*
7. Chandramouli C (2011): *Raral Urban distribution of population . <http://censusindia.gov.in/-prov-results/paper2/datatiles/india/rualurban2011>.*
8. Hu FB, Manson JE, Stampfer MJ, colditz G, Liu S, Solomon CG, (2001). *Diet lifestyle, and the risk of type-II diabetes mellitus in women. N Engl J Med 2001 sep; 345(11): 790-797*
9. *Diabetes in south east Asia: An update for (2013) for the IDF Diabetes Atlas, 6th edition.*
10. world Health organization. *Global Status report on non-communicable diseases 2014 [online] 2014 cited 2016 Dec.*
11. Zeng,Q,Chen XJ,He YT, ZM ,Wu YX Lin K.*Body Composition and metabolic syndrome in Patients with T1DM. World J Diabetes.2024;15:81-91.doi:10.4239/wjd.V15.i1.81.*
12. *American diabetes association, standards of medical care in Diabetes 2021.2021 jan;44(suppl) :S53-S72 (PubMed)*
13. www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov